

**PRACTICAL AND TECHNOLOGICAL TECHNOLOGY OF TEACHING
FOREIGN LANGUAGES TO PROFESSIONAL TEACHERS**

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Annotation. One of the important tasks of our research is the analysis of the model curriculum, curricula, materials, manuals, literature used in the teaching of English to students of non-philological disciplines (history, chemistry, etc.). The main purpose of this is to study the practical role of the problem of professional approach in improving the effectiveness of teaching English to higher education students.

Keywords: Pedagogy, subject, procedural, skill, qualification, terminology

Method: In the classification of modern pedagogy, textbooks are educational guides designed to expand and better master the knowledge given in the curriculum, and the topics presented in the science program are briefly reflected in the materials provided to students of history and chemistry. Main educational literature, anthologies, reference books, dictionaries, adapted printed texts in a foreign language, sets of tasks and exercises, methodical manuals for independent practical training, etc. For example, "Complete IELTS-2016" by J.Brookhard and B.Jakeman, introduction to international legal English by A.Kroys-linder and M.Firs (2008), K.Mason and global legal English, P.Atkins The lowers English language cursebook (2007) by Lower, in the process of developing textbooks, great attention was paid to the development of textbook functions. Analyzing the work of a number of scientists (Antonova, Tyurina 2002, Kroyevsky 2005, Lerner 1991, Skatkin 2006, Cherepovskaya 2005), we present the system of textbook functions in the form of a diagram in the framework of vocational education.

The control function of the textbook is shown in the upper part of the diagram. It plays the most important role in mastering the selected educational content. textbooks contain not only the subject itself, but also the methods of mastering it by students. The control function includes recommendations and instructions for organizing the learning process for students, as well as a set of recommendations that allow students to learn independently, helping students to clearly understand the educational goals. Therefore, in the development of exercises and tasks, the development of student activity is in the first place.

Research

The communicative function is that; A foreign language textbook ensures the gradual acquisition of communicative competence. The information function, in addition to information of a linguistic nature, the foreign language textbook contains information related to the topic. When developing a vocationally oriented study guide, we should carefully select texts that are useful for students to acquire professional competence in a foreign language.

Textbook visual aids often do not meet the needs of students. For example, in the complete IELTS guide used by universities, the texts and exercises focus on developing the skills for the users to successfully pass the respective exams. Currently, university entrance exams require IELTS and CEFR certificates for non-philological fields. The information in the textbook on the function of educational development in the educational directions of the future generation also creates a basis for expanding the world views of students.

Mainly, the relevance of the textbook to interdisciplinary activities in the educational process plays a big role in the educational environment. That is, the task of vocational orientation is to establish a connection between the educational process and the future teacher's profession, to reflect professional activity in educational materials. the function of self-control consists in rational organization of textbook learning activities, acquisition of knowledge and skills. the self-education function ensures that the student acquires the skills of orientation and cooperation with professional resources.

It should be noted that the lack of sufficient materials for the implementation of the goals and tasks set in the educational programs approved by the universities leads to a number of problems for teachers. For example, materials from different sources make it difficult for the teacher and the students to absorb the material presented.

In conclusion, it should be said that the purpose of creating a textbook for professional education is to allow future specialists to understand and justify the connection between the planned results of their activities, in-depth mastering of the selected educational content in the activities of teachers and students, and the development of all the above functions of the manual.

Currently, pedagogical technology is widely used, that is, in addition to teaching methods, the issues of understanding the purpose and tasks of teaching, developing the content of teaching, methods, and choosing teaching aids are considered. If we classify the design of pedagogical processes, if we focus on the researches of A.M.Navikov, it is expected that during the development of

pedagogical technology, the result of the object of design will gradually become more complicated due to many factors.

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